

The Continuity of Experience Principle: A Deweyan Interpretation of Recapitulation Theory¹

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Introduction

At the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, recapitulation theory greatly influenced most American social scientists. This interpretative scheme, according to which the development of the child (ontogenesis) recapitulated or reproduced that of humanity as a race (phylogenesis), had numerous pedagogical applications that took varying forms depending on the authors, their orientations, and their particular fields of study. The major impact of this theory upon turn-of-century scholars is now well known.² Less known, however, is the determining influence of this theory upon John Dewey's pedagogy.

Among the abundant literature available on Dewey, two prominent scholars have confronted this issue directly: Herbert M. Kliebard (1995) and Thomas D. Fallace (2009; 2010; 2011; 2012). In his *Struggle for the American Curriculum, 1893-1958*, Kliebard (1995) devotes a chapter to the description of Dewey's pedagogical ideas, especially as related to the curriculum of the Laboratory School. Kliebard accurately shows how Dewey tried to achieve a synthesis between the ideas of two opposing interest groups, the "humanists" and the "developmentalists," taking his own interpretation of recapitulation theory and trying "to reconstruct it in the curriculum of the Laboratory School" (p. 47; p. 61). Kliebard thus highlights the determining role played by recapitulation theory in shaping the curriculum of the Laboratory School. In a series of articles and books, Fallace (2009; 2010), building upon Kliebard's work, further develops some of Kliebard's conclusions, not only arguing that recapitulation theory "served as the foundation of the entire curriculum of the laboratory school, guiding both theory and practice" (Fallace, 2009, p. 383), but also that, during the Chicago period (1894-1904), Dewey was in fact a genetic psychologist, i.e. a thinker who believed that "human evolution involves intellectual growth, that this growth occurs through stages, and that each stage incorporates the prior one" (Fallace, 2010, p. 131). If both Kliebard and Fallace brilliantly describe the impact of recapitulation theory upon Dewey's curriculum at the Laboratory School, though, they have not explored the entanglement between Dewey's continuity of experience principle and recapitulation.

The reflections contained in this paper seek to corroborate some of the conclusions both Kliebard

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² See especially Egan (2004); Fallace, "Repeating the Race Experience" (2009); Gould (1977); and Stocking (1968).

and Fallace reached, but they also carry with them the aim of extending these conclusions one step further by showing the close relationship that exists between Dewey's continuity of experience principle and recapitulation theory. Indeed, if Dewey evoked recapitulation theory in a number of works, particularly those written during the Chicago period, the continuity of experience principle pervades his entire opus of educational and pedagogical writings. With this principle, which is nowhere better illustrated than in his famous essay "The Child and the Curriculum," Dewey (1902a) subscribed to the beliefs that the experiences of the child and that of humanity are simply two limits that define the educational process. Education is to be conceived as a continuous reconstruction of experience "moving from the child's present experience out into that represented by the organized bodies of truth that we call studies" (p. 278), i.e., by human experience throughout history. Therefore, humanity has progressed through a series of stages that constitute as many steps as those a child takes in the course of his/her own development.

Thus, I argue that, throughout his educational writings, Dewey was in fact struggling with the evolutionary scheme in which his entire thinking is rooted. He was indeed constantly trying to stand aloof from a strictly biological interpretation of recapitulation theory, but without renouncing such an evolutionary perspective. With his continuity of experience principle, Dewey developed his own interpretation of recapitulation theory in education as viewed in light of his philosophy of experience. This theory constitutes the very foundation and the architectonic principle of his entire pedagogy. I therefore demonstrate, first, that Dewey was not so much a genetic psychologist as an educational philosopher who used recapitulation theory to lend scientific support to his pedagogical ideas at the turn of the 19th-and 20th-centuries; and second, that it is this close relationship between the continuity of experience principle and recapitulation theory that clarifies the specific sense given to the *via media*, or the "creative synthesis"—as Kliebard (1999, p. 111) puts it—that Dewey tried to achieve throughout his educational writings. To demonstrate this, the following essay analyzes, first, the continuity of experience principle, and second, Dewey's stage theory of development in both the child and the human race.

1. The Continuity of Experience Principle

The continuity of experience principle is, together with the notion of growth, John Dewey's educational philosophy's most fundamental principle.¹ This principle is best revealed in his 1902 essay "The Child and the Curriculum." Dewey opens this essay by acknowledging the major discrepancies that exist between the child and the curriculum. He sums these up as follows: first, the contrast between the narrow but personal world of the child and the impersonal and infinitely extended world of space and time that one finds in the curriculum; second, the discordance between the unity of the child's life and the specializations and divisions of the school subjects; and third, the opposition between the practical and emotional bonds of child life and the rather remote and abstract principle of classification and arrangement that prevails in school knowledge. In these elements of conflict between the child and the curriculum, Dewey (1902a) explains, "educational sects" take root (p. 278).

¹ In a major book on Dewey, philosopher Thomas M. Alexander has demonstrated that the principle of continuity "is the key to Dewey's metaphysics" (*John Dewey's Theory of Art, Experience and Nature*, p. xvii; see also chapter 3).

Dewey thus stages the antinomy, or contradiction, between a doctrine of discipline—the child has to surrender to the logical order of the constituted school subjects—and a doctrine centered on the child’s interest—all studies are subservient to the child’s growth. Though one might be tempted to believe that Dewey took his cues from the latter doctrine, he tried instead to find a *via media*, a middle way that would solve the conflict that lay at the very heart of this opposition. This *via media* can be stated as follows: Even when the child, with his own living interests, powers, and capacities, stands in the foreground and is the central concern in education, reference to the constituted school disciplines should not be abandoned. This idea is well expressed in the following passage from Dewey’s (1902a) essay:

Abandon the notion of subject-matter as something fixed and ready-made in itself, outside the child’s experience; cease thinking of the child’s experience as also something hard and fast; see it as something fluent, embryonic, vital; and *we realize that the child and the curriculum are simply two limits which define a single process. Just as two points define a straight line, so the present standpoint of the child and the facts and truths of studies define instruction. It is continuous reconstruction, moving from the child’s present experience out into that represented by the organized bodies of truth that we call studies.* (p. 278; emphasis added)

For Dewey (1902a), the point is to get rid of the notion that there is a difference of nature between the child’s crude experience and the different studies that constitute the curriculum. Instead, he argues for the need to incorporate the idea of continuity between the child and the curriculum because, in the final instance, the sciences themselves, which the child has to learn, have grown out of ordinary experience, i.e., out of the “child’s present crude impulses in counting, measuring, and arranging things in rhythmic series” (p. 282).

The various studies, arithmetic, geography, language, botany, etc., *are themselves experience—they are that of the race. They embody the cumulative outcome of the efforts, the strivings, and successes of the human race generation after generation.* They present this, not as a mere accumulation, not as a miscellaneous heap of separate bits of experience, but in some organized and systematized way—that is, as reflectively formulated. (p. 278; emphasis added)

No longer conceived of “as something fixed and ready-made in itself, outside the child’s experience,” but as embodying “the cumulative outcome of the efforts, the strivings, and successes of the human race generation after generation,” the curriculum, in the Deweyan perspective, identifies itself with the process of human civilization, i.e., the growth process. The curriculum is then conceived as the repository of the experiences humanity has had throughout history, i.e., the “warranted assertabilities,” or knowledge, that adults have developed over the centuries in order to solve the practical problems they faced within their environment.

Consequently, the child and the curriculum are conceived as the initial and final terms of a single process: The educative or growth process itself. This continuity of experience principle allows Dewey to relate the child’s individual nature to the social culture as expressed in the curriculum. With this analysis, Dewey is implicitly claiming that the child’s only possible career and destiny are found in the idea that “ontogeny recapitulates phylogeny.” In saying that the child’s experience

is the initial term of a continuous process whose final term is human experience and knowledge in its present state, Dewey subscribed to the belief that throughout history humanity has progressed through a series of stages that constitute as many steps as those the child has to take in the course of his own development, and that the child finds himself at the beginning stage of that process, namely at the level of the primitive. Indeed, throughout his pedagogical and educational writings, Dewey constantly brings the child's mind back to the level of the primitive or savage, thus extracting the notion of primitivity from its anthropological base in order to adapt it to child psychology:

Many anthropologists have told us there are certain identities in the child [*sic*] interests with those of primitive life. There is a sort of natural recurrence of the child mind to the typical activities of primitive peoples; witness the hut which the boy likes to build in the yard, playing hunt, with bows, arrows, spears, and so on. (Dewey, 1900a, p. 111)

For Dewey, even in our modern western societies, the child perceives reality and behaves essentially like a primitive. The child's vision "is essentially that of the savage; being adapted to seeing large and somewhat remote objects in the mass, not near-by objects in detail" (Dewey, 1898, pp. 259-60). Dewey adds, "both primitive man and the child are decidedly motor in their activity. Both are interested in objects and materials, not from a contemplative or theoretical standpoint, but from the standpoint of what can be done with them, and what can be got out of them" (1901a, p. 233). If the child's experience is similar to that of the primitive, and if the end of the educative process is the curriculum, i.e., present human experience and knowledge, then the child's development mimics on a small scale the development of humanity throughout history. Thus, with this idea of the continuity between the child and the curriculum, Dewey contends that the child, as well as humanity throughout history, develops and progresses from primitivity to scientificity; education, then, consisted of supplying the conditions which will enable the child to reconstruct, in a few short months and years, the experience of the human race as embodied in the curriculum. This idea is nowhere better illustrated than in the following passage from *Democracy and Education* (1916):

Prior human efforts have made over natural conditions.... Every domesticated plant and animal, every tool, every utensil, every appliance, every manufactured article, every esthetic decoration, every work of art means a transformation of conditions once hostile or indifferent to characteristic human activities into friendly and favoring conditions. *Because the activities of children today are controlled by these selected and charged stimuli, children are able to traverse in a short lifetime what the race has needed slow, tortured ages to attain.* The dice have been loaded by all the successes which have preceded. (p. 44; emphasis added)

In the Deweyan perspective, it is only because the school and the teacher arrange the conditions which will enable children to reconstruct the human experience embodied in the curriculum that they are actually able to do so. It is only *because* "the activities of children today are controlled by these selected and charged stimuli" that "*children are able*" to reenact the experiences humanity has had throughout history. Here, Dewey is careful to stand aloof from a strictly biological recapitulation theory: he clearly rejects the approaches to biological recapitulation made by

Herbert Spencer and G. Stanley Hall.¹ For Dewey, children, left on their own, are unable to achieve what humanity has accomplished throughout its history. Children must be guided: There is a need for a concerted action, an action designed to supply the conditions which will guide children's growth so that they can reconstruct human experience. It is only through education, as a conscious plan, that children can recapitulate, in a short amount of time, the progress of humanity throughout the ages. In this way, education is not recapitulation in a strictly biological sense. It is the business of the teacher, through a deep knowledge of the curriculum, to direct children's experience in such a way as to avoid the errors and wanderings of their ancestors so that they are able to recapitulate "in a short lifetime" the human experience embodied in the curriculum. It is in this sense that "The dice have been loaded by all the successes which have preceded."²

For Dewey (1902a), education is thus to be conceived as a continuous reconstruction of experience "moving from the child's present experience out into that represented by the organized bodies of truth that we call studies." In these conditions, the curriculum simply represents "the possibilities

¹ On this matter, see Herbert Spencer's *Essays on Education* (1949) and Hall's *Adolescence* (1904), "The Contents of Children's Minds" (1883), and *Educational Problems*, 2 vols. (New York: D. Appleton, 1911).

² In Dewey's view, all the progress humanity has made in knowledge, science, and correlated tools and technology throughout the centuries has led to a transformation of the environment we live in. Such a transformation has great implications for education. Teachers and educators have to use what Dewey calls "*weighted* stimuli" in order to promote child growth. As he puts it:

The advance of civilization means that a larger number of natural forces and objects have been transformed into instrumentalities of action, into means for securing ends. We start not so much with superior capacities as with superior stimuli for evocation and direction; we have *weighted* stimuli....

Stimuli conducive to economical and effective response, such as our system of roads and means of transportation, our ready command of heat, light, and electricity, our readymade machines and apparatus for every purpose, do not, by themselves or in their aggregate, constitute a civilization. But the uses to which they are put are civilization, and without the things the uses would be impossible. Time otherwise devoted to wrestling a livelihood from a grudging environment and securing a precarious protection against its inclemencies is freed. A body of knowledge is transmitted, the legitimacy of which is guaranteed by the fact that the physical equipment in which it is incarnated leads to results that square with the other facts of nature. Thus these appliances of art supply a protection, perhaps our chief protection, against a recrudescence of these superstitious beliefs, those fanciful myths and infertile imaginings about nature in which so much of the best intellectual power of the past has been spent....

Intentional education signifies ... a specially selected environment, the selection being made on the basis of materials and method specifically promoting growth in the desired direction. (*Democracy and Education*, 1916, p. 44-45)

of development inherent in the child's immediate crude experience" (1902a, p. 278-279). Thus, one has but to see the degree to which the child's experience already contains, in germ, the interests, motives and attitudes that operated in the organization and elaboration of the curriculum as it stood at the time Dewey wrote. From a pedagogical standpoint, the curriculum then serves first and foremost as a revealing instrument: "The subject-matter of science and history and art serves to reveal the real child" to the teacher, i.e., to locate the child's present position along the educational process. Thus the teacher can "see the step the child needs to take just here and now" (p. 278). As Dewey (1902a) puts it at the end of his essay,

the value of the formulated wealth of knowledge that makes up the course of study is that it may enable the educator *to determine the environment of the child*, and thus by indirection to direct. Its primary value, its primary indication, is for the teacher, not for the child. It says to the teacher: Such and such are the capacities, the fulfillments, in truth and beauty and behavior, open to these children. Now see to it that day by day the conditions are such that *their own activities* move inevitably in this direction, toward such culmination of themselves. Let the child's nature fulfill its own destiny, revealed to you in whatever of science and art and industry the world now holds as its own. (p. 291; Dewey's emphasis)

The curriculum's usefulness thus consists in its indicating to the teacher the different means to put at the child's disposal in the different fields of knowledge. The educator's task is then much more difficult than that of the teacher in a traditional or conventional school. Indeed, in the Deweyan perspective, the teacher does not, strictly speaking, hold class; his/her role is not to teach school subjects in their systematic progression; he/she is not a mediator of the culture to pupils. His/her task is much more sophisticated. It is similar to that of Rousseau's governor: he/she has to arrange an environment. This environment must be arranged in such a way that the child will be able to reenact human experience without teacher intervention. Indeed, the Deweyan teacher or educator has to "psychologize" (p. 285) the curriculum, i.e., reinstate into the child's present and crude experience the subject matter of the studies, or branches of learning, by means of a specific environment: the classroom.

With this continuity of experience principle, Dewey thus proposes an original version of recapitulation theory in education: his entire pedagogical work consists of a reinterpretation, based on his philosophy of experience, of that theory. At the time, this recapitulation theory lent scientific support to Dewey's pedagogical and educational philosophy. In fact, it was the very foundation of and the architectonic principle of his entire educational and pedagogical approach. It is this close relationship between the continuity of experience principle and recapitulation theory that clarifies the specific sense given to the *via media*, or middle way, that Dewey tried to generate throughout his educational writings. The philosopher was thus highlighting the tension that existed in American academia at the time between two rival genetic psychologies of education: that of G. Stanley Hall and Herbert Spencer, which was rooted in the neo-Lamarckian principle of the inheritance of acquired characteristics, and his own reinterpretation, closer to that of James Mark Baldwin, who denied such principles and considered that experience matters in education, and that culture is cumulative.¹ Such a reinterpretation implied a clear departure from genetic psychology

¹ See Baldwin, *Elements of Psychology* (1893) and *Mental Development in the Child and in the Race* (1894).

while still subscribing to its main idea, namely, that “ontogeny recapitulates phylogeny.” Here, one must bear in mind that Dewey (1916) does not reduce the notion of education to that of life or growth: “Our net conclusion is that life is development, and that developing, growing, is life. Translated into its educational equivalents, that means (i) that the educational process has no end beyond itself; it is its own end; and that (ii) the educational process is one of continual reorganizing, reconstructing, transforming” (p. 59). Inasmuch as life itself is development, or growth, it is education, i.e., learning through interaction with the environment. There is then no end to the educational process. On the other hand, insofar as education is a conscious plan or an intentional business, a fostering of the child’s growth, it has a specific end: to represent the experience of the human race, i.e., the state of human knowledge imbedded in the curriculum. As Dewey (1902a) put it, “the facts and truths that enter into the child’s present experience, and those contained in the subject-matter of studies, are the initial and final terms of one reality. To oppose one to the other is to oppose the infancy and maturity of the same growing life; it is to set the moving tendency and the final result of the same process over against each other; it is to hold that the nature and the destiny of the child war with each other” (p. 278). From a pedagogical standpoint, Dewey (1902a) thus contended that the teacher is incapable of guiding the child’s growth if the adult knowledge is not “drawn upon as revealing the possible career open to the child” (p. 279). In other words, “the systematized and defined experience of the adult mind is of value to us in interpreting the child’s life as it immediately shows itself, and in passing on to guidance or direction” (p. 283).

Indeed, Dewey’s pedagogy is entirely rooted in recapitulation theory understood in this way. Without it, the experience of humanity throughout history is not the end of a single process—the educational or growth process—whose initial term is the child’s experience. Without it, the curriculum does not reveal “the real child to us”; the teacher is thus incapable of knowing “in what direction the present experience [of the child] is moving” (p. 279). Direction, guidance, and even education are then impossible, because the teacher simply cannot “see to it that day by day the conditions are such that *their own activities* [i.e., those of the children] move inevitably in this direction, toward such culmination of themselves”; he simply cannot “let the child’s nature fulfill its own destiny” (p. 291), because this destiny is not revealed to him in the curriculum, which is no longer conceived as the final terminus of the educational process. Dewey puts it thus in a fascinating passage from his 1938 work “Experience and Education”:

Every experience is a moving force. *Its value can be judged only on the ground of what it moves toward and into.* The greater maturity of experience which should belong to the adult as educator puts him in position *to evaluate each experience of the young* in a way which the one having the less mature experience cannot do. It is then the business of the educator *to see in what direction an experience is heading.* There is no point in his being more mature if, instead of using his greater insight to help organize the conditions of the experience of the immature, he throws away his insight. Failure to take the moving force of an experience into account so as to judge and direct it on the ground of what it is moving into means *disloyalty to the principle of experience itself.* (p. 21; emphasis added)

If one does not presuppose or accept, as Dewey did throughout his educational and pedagogical writings, the continuity of experience principle, which can be understood as Dewey’s own interpretation of recapitulation theory viewed in the light of his philosophy of experience (if one

is thus disloyal to this principle), one simply cannot evaluate or judge the child's experience, simply because one has no idea of what it moves toward and into. Therefore, without this continuity of experience principle, Dewey's pedagogy falls.

If Dewey considered education to be a process whose initial and final terms are the child's experience and the curriculum, i.e., the experience humanity as a race has had throughout history, the philosopher also isolated a series of intermediate stages between these initial and final terms. These intermediate stages are all *subsumed* in Dewey's continuity of experience principle. These stages of the child's development, from the Deweyan perspective, constitute just as many moments of the civilization process, of the evolution of the human logical thought.

2. John Dewey's Stage Theory of Development

At the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, the social sciences were pervaded with the idea that the human mind, whether that of the individual or that of humanity as a race, progressed through a series of developmental stages.¹ This idea was commonplace at the time, and constituted a *topos* in American social science scholarship. In that regard, John Dewey was not an exception: like many of his peers, he subscribed to the belief that children develop through a series of stages that corresponds with the logical growth of the human race. In his pedagogical writings, Dewey thus proposed, as Thomas D. Fallace (2010; 2011) shows in "The Mind at Every Stage" and *Dewey and the Dilemma of Race*, a typology of the stages of the child's growth that was linked with another one: the four stages of human logical thought. In the following pages, we will briefly review these two typologies that Fallace studies in depth elsewhere.

2.1. Stages of child development

Dewey insisted on the fact that his typology grew not so much out of anthropology, but from psychology and child-study (Dewey and McLellan, 1895, p. 18). According to Fallace (2010), this typology is composed of four different stages:

The educative period of life, covering the first twenty to twenty-five years, may be roughly subdivided into four stages: (1) Early infancy, lasting two or two and a half years; (2) Later infancy, extending to the sixth or seventh year; (3) Childhood to the thirteenth or fourteenth year; and (4) Youth. (Dewey, 1900b, p. 194)

2.1.1. Early infancy

Early infancy, which lasts until the child's thirtieth month, is a sensitive-motor stage during which the child learns to master his body. For Dewey, sensitive observations and motor interactions with the environment are early infancy's keynote features (Fallace, 2010, pp. 137-139; Tanner. 2016, p. 13).

As Dewey explains it, during the first six months of life, the child gains a certain degree of "bodily

¹ This idea served as the basis for the developmental approach in psychology and education, notably that of Jean Piaget. On this issue, see Boring (1950); Egan (2004); Fallace, "Recapitulation Theory" (2012); Gould (1977); and Stocking (1968; 1987).

control”; he or she learns “a few simple adjustments,” i.e., to master and coordinate his sensitive organs. This mastery is followed by the construction of “a simple world of objects.” The child then goes on to learn “to manage the body, not only at rest, but also in motion,” that is, “to creep and walk.” The child then extends acquaintance with the things that surround him or her, thus making “simple and crude *connections* of objects.” At the age of twelve or fifteen months, the instinct of imitation develops: the child “now endeavors to make the simple movements of hand, of vocal organs, etc., already in his possession the instruments of reproducing what his eye and his ear report to him of the world about him” (Dewey and McLellan. 1895, pp. 15-16). For Dewey, this second period lasts approximately until the child is thirty months old.

2.1.2. *Later infancy*

Later infancy, which lasts until the age of seven, is a stage in which the child develops a conscious control of and an awareness of his body and activities: It is the “period of ideal coordination,” of “imaginative activities,” and of the “play period” (Dewey, 1895, p. 299).

This second stage constitutes the first stage of elementary education. It is “characterized by directness of social and personal interests, and by directness and promptness of relationship between impressions, ideas, and action” (Dewey, 1900a, p. 73). Dewey (1896) considers this stage to be one “of Free Use of Formed Co-ordinations” (p. 310). From a pedagogical standpoint, social occupations should stand in the foreground, because “in connection with these occupations the historic development of man is recapitulated” (Dewey, 1900a, p. 14).

2.1.3. *Childhood*

Childhood is the “period of symbolism, of recognition of meaning, of significance,” and lasts until the age of thirteen (Dewey and McLellan, 1895, p. 17). This period is especially important for Dewey because, according to him, it is a “period of intense motor activity” during which the child’s “energy is ... being consumed in the building up of connections and adjustments which refine and complicate the powers already attained.” At this point, “a distinctive intellectual interest” (Dewey, 1895, p. 299) emerges, fostering the emergence of other interests for tools and symbols. From a pedagogical standpoint, childhood is the second stage of elementary education. The three R’s are then introduced as “the keys which will unlock to the child the wealth of social capital which lies beyond the possible range of his limited individual experience” (Dewey, 1900a, p. 77). Just as in the earlier stage, teaching always occurs through social occupations because “they, more than any other study, more than reading or geography, story-telling or myth, evoke and direct what is most fundamental and vital in the child; that in which he is the heir of all the ages, and through which he recapitulates the progress of the race” (Dewey, 1901a, p. 235).

2.1.4. *Youth*

According to Dewey (1900b), youth lasts until the age of twenty or twenty-five and marks “the epoch of securing the final adjustment on the part of the individual of himself to the fundamental features of life.” It is the stage during which the young individual’s development and that of the race in its history meet. Dewey subdivided this stage into two periods: “That of pubescence from ... thirteen to eighteen,” and “that of adolescence proper.” Pubescence is “a period of tremendous

enlargement of the sphere of interests, of the range of ideas and of stimuli of action” (p. 216). Then an “interest in reflective analysis,” an “introspective interest,” and a “conscious aesthetic interest” arise and ripen (Dewey, 1895, p. 299). As for adolescence, Dewey considered it to be the “reflective period.” From this moment on the individual seeks to contribute actively to the production of new knowledge and scholarship as well as to the betterment of society. “In history, in literature, in science, the tendency at this time is to see larger wholes, to try to gather together the facts otherwise scattered and to mass them as parts in the comprehensive whole.” At this stage, there is a shifting of the center of gravity in interest from the individual to the race; the adolescent “tends to go beyond the limitations of his own particular experiences, to escape from the bonds of his own individual limitations and to discover and lose himself in the world of humanity ... the world which the race has formed for itself” (Dewey, 1900b, p. 217). At this point, the young individual finishes reconstructing the experience of the human race, strictly speaking, and sets about contributing actively to the *construction* of that experience.

These four stages of child development are, by virtue of the continuity of experience principle, closely correlated to the steps through which mankind has progressed in history.

2.2. Stages of race development

As Fallace (2010) demonstrates, Dewey confronted directly the issue of the development of the human race through history in a 1900 article published in *The Philosophical Review* titled “Some Stages of Logical Thought” (1900c). In it, he exposed “a variety of modes of thinking, *easily recognizable in the progress of both the race and the individual*” (1900c, p. 465; emphasis added). The term “progress” is to be understood in the strict sense of the word, since these modes of thinking constituted, for Dewey, “some of the main stages through which thinking ... actually passes in its attempt to reach its most effective working; that is, the maximum of certainty” (p. 465). Dewey goes on to distinguish four stages of logical thought.

2.2.1. Primitive communities

In the first stage of logical thought, “ideas are treated as something fixed and static.” Drawing upon the social psychology scholarship of his time, Dewey (1900c) considered that “an apt illustration” of these fixed ideas was found “in the rules prevalent in primitive communities” (p. 468). These fixed ideas, these social customs, were “no less real than physical events”; indeed, they were “facts,” and carried “with them certain sanctions” which could go up to the physical suppression of the individual who departs from them. As Dewey (1900c) explains it, thought, in this stage, is pre-judgmental rather than judgmental: “The attitude is uncritical and dogmatic in the extreme—so much so that one might question whether it is to be properly designated as a stage of thinking” (p. 470). However, as the complexity of life advanced, “a certain degree of inquiring and critical attitude” emerges (p. 469), thus opening the way to the second stage of logical thought.

2.2.2. Ancient Greek societies

The emergence of this new way of thinking was due to a kind of inflation of customary rules: “As the scheduled stock of fixed ideas grows larger, their application to specific questions becomes more difficult, prolonged, and roundabout.” Consequently, a “hunting for the specific idea which

is appropriate” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 471) to each particular case begins. Individuals were forced to discuss and compare the different fixed ideas that existed in order to solve each particular problem the community faced. Judgment thus became “legislative.” According to Dewey (1900c), this second stage was typified in Hebrew history and, more specifically, in ancient Greek societies. In these societies, through meetings of assemblies, a new and constant emphasis was put upon discussion, thus creating “a marked departure from positive declaration of custom” (p. 472). Thus ancient Greek culture, where discussion was of paramount importance, contributed to a transformation of the individual himself: “He became a miniature social assemblage, in which pros and cons were brought into play struggling for the mastery—for final conclusion. In some such way we conceive reflection to be born.” However, as Dewey contended, under the Sophists’ influence, this culture of discussion led to a kind of subjectivism and skepticism; “Where all was fixity, now all is instability: where all was certitude, nothing now exists save personal opinion based on prejudice, interest, or arbitrary choice” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 473).

2.2.3. *Medieval Scholasticism*

The third stage of logical thought was that of “medieval scholasticism” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 482). This third period, better illustrated in “the reaction of the Socratic school against the Sophistic” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 475), is characterized by the acceptance of certain “fundamental truths unquestioned and unquestionable, self-evident and self-evidencing, neither established nor modified by thought, but standing firm in their own right” (1900c, p. 478)—namely Aristotelian logic. With this logic affording “the precise instrumentality through which the vague and chaotic details of life could be reduced to order by subjecting them to the terms of authoritative rules” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 479), a new mode of thinking emerged, which took the syllogism form. This new mode of thinking then led to “the transformation of discussion into reasoning, of subjective reflection into method of proof” (1900c, p. 476). However, according to Dewey (1900c), this thought remained narrow because it never questioned the fixed premises of the syllogism; reasoning in this stage then had only a formal value, thus contrasting with the expert or laboratory thought, which constitutes the last and final stage of logical thought.

2.2.4. *Modern science and democracy*

“Modern scientific procedure,” “inductive and empirical science,” defined “the ideal and limit of this process” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 486). In this stage, thought took the form of inference: “*Inventio* is more important than *judicium*, discovery than ‘proof’” (Dewey, 1900c, p. 483). This new form of thinking was that of the expert who strove to discover new ways of explaining the world. Theories and ideas were then no longer “fixed,” “static,” or “ultimate”; they were no longer outside of the world of experience; they were no longer part of a logically hierarchical order founded by an idea considered to be “the ultimate truth.” Rather, as Dewey (1900c) explained, “there is substituted for the hierarchical world, in which each degree in the scale has its righteousness imputed from above, a world homogeneous in structure and in the scheme of its parts” (p. 485). In this stage, sciences gradually specialize and modern disciplines emerge. According to Dewey (1900c), this specialization correlates to democracy: “When interest is occupied in finding out what anything and everything is ... the observable world is a democracy” (p. 485).

Thus, Dewey distinguished four stages—albeit historically unconvincing—by which logical

thought has passed throughout history in order to reach its most effective working, namely scientific and democratic modern thinking. By this means, Dewey shows that thinking, as a knowing process, progressively acquires its knowledge in a genesis similar to that of ontogenesis. The history of logical thinking, as well as that of the child's development, is the history of a progressive de-centering from auto-centered and purely subjective conceptions to a scientific mode of thinking focused on the object.

If Fallace (2010) accurately describes these stages of child's growth and of human logical thought, saying that "humans develop through distinct, observable stages of consciousness that correspond with the intellectual development of the race" (p. 129), he overestimates the degree to which Dewey was a genetic psychologist. Indeed, as we saw earlier, if Dewey did believe that a child has to reconstruct the experience the human race has had throughout history, this did not imply that he believed that this child learned and thought differently from the civilized adult. On the contrary, as early as 1899 Dewey stressed the importance of recognizing the "psychological identity" between the child and the adult:

With the adult we unquestioningly assume that an attitude of personal inquiry, based upon the possession of a problem which interests and absorbs, is a necessary precondition of mental growth. With the child we assume that the precondition is rather the willing disposition which makes him ready to submit to any problem and material presented from without. *Alertness* is our ideal in one case; *docility* in the other. With one we assume that power of attention develops in dealing with problems which make a personal appeal, and through personal responsibility for determining what is relevant. With the other we provide next to no opportunities for the evolution of problems out of immediate experience, and allow next to no free mental play for selecting, assorting and adapting the experience and ideas that make for their solution. *How profound a revolution in the position and service of text-book and teacher, and in methods of instruction depending therefrom, would be effected by a sincere recognition of the psychological identity of child and adult in these respects can with difficulty be realized.* (Dewey, 1901b, p. 134-135; emphasis added)

As Robert B. Westbrook (1991) demonstrates, "it was precisely this revolution that Dewey aimed to effect" in his educational and pedagogical writings (p. 98). In the Deweyan perspective, one then must sincerely recognize this "psychological identity" of child and adult; both learn in the exact same way through interaction with their environment. As Dewey (1902b) explained in his 1902 essay on savage mind, "the biological point of view commits us to the conviction that mind, whatever else it may be, is at least an organ of service for the control of environment in relation to the ends of the life process" (p. 41). Thus, the child, the savage, and the civilized adult must all be considered first and foremost "intensely active" beings who think and learn from experience by trying to resolve the specific problem they face in their own environment. Consequently, the child, the primitive, the adolescent and the adult can all be considered "social constructivists" (Fallace, 2010, p. 146). This allows us to understand the specific sense Dewey (1900a) gave to education when he said, "The question of education is the question of taking hold of [the] activities [of the child], of giving them direction" (p. 25). The only difference that exists between the child, the savage, and the civilized adult is that they are located at various "stage[s] and phase[s] of the development of experience" (Dewey, 1902a, p. 285), that is, at different locations along a

hierarchical process that can be represented in terms of verticality, i.e., Dewey's continuity of experience principle. Consequently, there is no discontinuity (Prawat, 2000) or "shift" (Fallace, 2010, p. 146) in Dewey's pedagogy, but rather continuity (Garrison, 2001), because the continuity of experience principle pervades the philosopher's entire educational writings, from his earlier to his later works, from "My Pedagogic Creed" (1897) to "Experience and Education" (1938). That this continuity of experience principle is a reinterpretation of recapitulation theory viewed in the light of Dewey's philosophy of experience is fraught with implications regarding the limitations of Dewey's own pedagogy. Indeed, one can see that Dewey was in fact struggling with the evolutionary scheme in which his entire thinking is rooted, but without renouncing such an evolutionary perspective. Here, Fallace (2009) is right when he argues for the need to understand Dewey in the intellectual currents of its time, showing that his pedagogical and educational writings carry with them hierarchical implications that cannot be dismissed easily (Fallace, "Repeating the Race Experience," 2009, p. 402).

Conclusion

In this paper, I have demonstrated that the continuity of experience principle, which lies at the heart of Dewey's educational and pedagogical work, consists fundamentally of a Deweyan reinterpretation of recapitulation theory in education, viewed in light of his philosophy of experience. This interpretation implies a clear departure from genetic psychology while still subscribing to its main idea, namely that "ontogeny recapitulates phylogeny." It is this close relationship between the continuity of experience principle and recapitulation theory that clarifies the specific sense given to the *via media*, or middle way, that Dewey tried to achieve throughout his educational writings. Dewey was thus an educational philosopher who used recapitulation theory to lend scientific support to his entire pedagogical and educational philosophy. Consequently, and despite the deep elaboration that characterized his work, one cannot consider Dewey's pedagogy and education without discussing, justifying, as well as bringing up to date the theoretical presuppositions that underlie them, particularly the specific meaning the philosopher gave to the continuity of experience principle. Indeed, far from being contingent or fortuitous, this principle lies at the very foundation of Dewey's entire educational and pedagogical philosophy.

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